

From Time to Time

Forty-five years ago, me and my friend decided to sneak into this big car race. Our plan was to arrive the night before, watch the mechanics working in the pits, and stay there so we could watch the race for free when they closed the gates.

While we were there, we figured we'd walk the entire racing circuit, just like the pro drivers do. That's when something in the sky caught our attention — a bright light changing colors, moving crazy fast.

It wasn't a plane. It wasn't a helicopter. The object stopped dead in the sky, then changed direction in an instant, crisscrossing above us like nothing bound by our physics. For a few mesmerizing minutes it kept on — accelerating, hovering, vanishing into the distance like there were no limits.

Then it came real close, stopped right there in front of us, and just... zoomed out and disappeared.

Up to this day, I know there's no technology on Earth that can do what we saw. Not forty-five years ago, and not even now. In my mind, it had something to do with time and speed. Like maybe they don't just move through space... they move through time itself.

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by Alberto Bueno de Paula